

ARE THE MILLENNIALS READY TO BE THE NEW NORMAL LEADERS?

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ABSTRACT

With four very different generations in the workplace, the chance of having intergenerational conflicts are high. It is the responsibility of leaders to minimize high turnover of young and productive workforce due to diverse preferences. Leadership behavior has been most widely used and followers could specifically evaluate the ability of their leader to reduce conflict in the multigenerational work environment. This research was undertaken to investigate differences in perceived leadership behavior among multigenerational superiors. This study gathered 321 respondents and One-Way ANOVA was performed to analyze the data. Result shows there is a significant difference in perceived leadership behavior among the multigenerational superiors. It reveals that multigenerational workforce has entrusted leadership to a large number of Gen Y. Gen Y superiors were perceived to have the ability to integrate, tolerate uncertainty, and use persuasion and argument effectively. These abilities are compulsory in this time of Covid-19 crisis.

Keywords: Gen Y, LBDQ-XII, Perceived Multigenerational Leadership Behaviors